

Thermal Studies on Oceanic Salts*

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Successive evaporations of sea bittern after desalting of sodium chloride gives Sels Mixts between 34 and 36° Be', mixed salt between 36 and 38° Be' and leaves behind a mother liquor rich in magnesium chloride. The fraction, Sels Mixts, is a mixture of sodium chloride and magnesium chloride in widely varying proportions (NaCl 55.0 to 65.0% and $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ 35.0 to 45.0%). The differential thermal analysis of the Sels Mixts with NaCl 58% and $MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$ 42% were conducted and the results are presented in the paper. The thermographs obtained show two prominent endothermal effects at 225° and 625° which are neither due to epsom salt nor due to sodium chloride. On the other hand, these endothermal peaks are indicative of formation of astrakainite—a double sulphate of sodium and magnesium, $Na_2SO_4 \cdot MgSO_4 \cdot 4H_2O$, in the system.

THE salt is manufactured from seawater by solar evaporation. As the evaporation proceeds, fractions of salts are precipitated out. Bittern is the mother liquor obtained after desalting of brine and is 2% of the original volume of brine. Successive evaporation of bittern gives Sels Mixts between 34° and 36° Be', mixed salt between 36° and 38° Be' and leaves a mother liquor rich in magnesium chloride. Sels Mixts is a mixture of sodium chloride and epsom salt in widely varying proportions (NaCl 55-65% and epsom salt 35-45%). It is the starting material for the manufacture of sodium sulphate. Sels Mixts is collected in the field in salt works and is stored for further processing.

Differential thermal studies of the system $NaCl \cdot MgSO_4$, comprising of the two constituents of the Sels Mixts were carried out. Two Analar salts were mixed in the ratio as given below (the ratio is the same as actually found in samples of Sels Mixts obtained from our Experimental Salt Farm):

NaCl	58.0 %
$MgSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$	42.0 %

Thermographs were taken of this synthetic mixture and also of the natural Sels Mixts and are given in Fig.1. Thermographs were recorded on the Sargent recorder model MR with chromel-alumel thermocouples. The sample and the reference material were packed in the holes of 8 mm dia and 12 mm depths drilled in the SS block. The sample holder with thermocouple were placed in the furnace vertically. The rate of heating was 10° per minute. Previously calcined Al_2O_3 was used as reference material and the temperature recorded were of this

reference material. Representative thermographs recorded are given in the Figure 1:

Fig 1

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- i) Curve, 'A' is for epsom salt, $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$
- ii) Curve 'B' is for synthetic mixture immediately after mixing.
- iii) Curve 'C' is for synthetic mixture after 75 days of mixing.
- iv) Curve 'D' is for synthetic mixture after 120 days of mixing.
- v) Curve 'E' is for natural Sels Mixts collected from the salt works.
- vi) Curve 'F' is for astrakanite.

The curves B, C, D & E show the following endothermal effects :

- i) The first change in thermal energy is at 55°
- ii) The second change begins at a temperature around 100° and is followed by a shoulder and a sharp peak at 138° .
- iii) Very prominent effect is observed at 225° .
- iv) The next effect is at 360°
- v) The endothermal peak is recorded at 625° and finally the sample melts at 675° .

Suppose there is no reaction in the system and the two salts, i.e., NaCl and $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ maintain their individual identity, the characteristic endothermic effects of epsom salt should only have been observed. The energy changes in the epsom salt are : at 52° when heptahydrate melts ; at 97° when hexahydrate melts ; at 107° when tetrahydrate dehydrates ; at 117° when tetrahydrate dehydrates ; at 138° when trihydrates dehydrates ; at 184° when dihydrate dehydrates ; at 340° when kieserite dehydrates ; and finally, at 1124° when anhydrous magnesium sulphate melts.

These energy changes for epsom salt are collected from the literature^{1,2} and compare very favourably with the data recorded and presented in Curve 'A'. Upto 138° , the energy changes in the curves B, C, D and E are comparable with those of epsom salt in the curve 'A' although at places the effects are overlapped and have resulted in shoulder formation. Beyond 138° , two important endothermal energy changes are recorded at 225° (Curve B, C, D, E & F) and at 625° (Curve D, E & F). These two effects can neither be ascribed to epsom salt nor to the sodium chloride the second salt of the system $\text{NaCl} \cdot \text{MgSO}_4$. Sodium chloride¹ is not affected by heat at lower temperatures but melts at 800° . These two effects at 225° and at 625° are therefore indicative of the formation of some other salt.

In the liquid (solution) phase and under controlled conditions, the two salts, i.e., NaCl and $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are known to undergo the following^{3,4} reactions :

Under the experimental conditions, the first reaction seems to be more plausible (in solid state also) as the two salts react to form a natural mineral, astrakanite. In the second reaction, sodium sulphate decahydrate, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, also known as Glauber's Salt, is formed. Glauber's Salt⁵ melts at 32.4° , boils at 102° , undergoes polymorphic transformation at 240° and finally melts at 884° . In the curve B, C, D & E, no energy change is noticed either at 32.4° or at 240° and, therefore, it can be concluded that Glauber's Salt is not formed in the system.

Two sharp effects observed in the curves B, C, D and E at 225° and 625° , as referred to above, are characteristic of astrakanite and loweite (Curve F). The double sulphate of sodium and magnesium, astrakanite, becomes anhydrous at 225° by losing remaining two molecules of water (the two having earlier been lost at 110°) and decomposes at 625° . The sensitivity⁶ of these two thermal energy changes (one at 225° and the other at 625°) has been recorded as 2-5 mole %, on the lower side, in a mixture of salt system. Hence, it can be concluded that astrakanite is formed by the reaction of sodium chloride and epsom salt in the solid phase.

Coming to the endothermal effects beginning around 98° , followed by a shoulder and a Break at 138° , the first change in energy is recorded when the epsom salt melts (Curve B, C, D and E). The melt boils at 107° . It is around this temperature that astrakanite loses two molecules of water and forms loweite. All these effects are projected in the form of a shoulder which is actually cumulative effect of :

- i) dehydration of hexahydrate, 98°
- ii) dehydration of astrakanite, when it loses two molecules of water and forms loweite ; 110°
- iii) dehydration of tetrahydrate, 117°
- iv) melting of bischoffite, the second reaction product, formed during the reaction in equation I.
- v) the final peak at 138° for the dehydration of $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$

The endothermal effect observed around 350° is indicative of the complete dehydration of magnesium sulphate through kieserite. Anhydrous magnesium sulphate is formed at this stage.

It can be concluded that astrakanite is formed from the Sels Mixts on storing. Fresh samples do not show any such tendencies. However, much more

work on DTA, thermodynamic calculations and X-ray diffraction is necessary before a clear picture of the mechanism of reaction can be fully established.

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